

Synthesis and biological significance of pyrano pyrazoles from 8,9-dimethyl-3-acetoacetyl pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione

Zeba N. Siddiqui* and Mohammad Asad

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail: siddiqui_zeba@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : 6,7-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxycoumarin **1** was treated with triacetic acid lactone **2** in heating methanol to afford 8,9-dimethyl-3-acetoacetyl pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione **3**. The compound **3** was transformed to pyrano pyrazole derivatives **4a-c** by treatment with nitrogen bases such as hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine and hydrazinobenzothiazole. The structure of all compounds was established on the basis of spectroscopic studies and screened for their antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities.

Keywords : 6,7-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxycoumarin, 8,9-dimethyl-3-acetoacetyl pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione, triacetic acid lactone, pyrano pyrazoles, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities.

Introduction

Heterocycles are much sought after compounds in recent years because of their pronounced pharmacological activities. They are acquiring much significance in the field of drug designing processes. Among various types of heterocyclic compounds, pyrazole framework plays important role in biologically active compounds. They are potent analgesic and antipyretic agents^{1,2}. Various pyrazole based compounds have been reported for exhibiting activities such as antidiabetic³, antitumor⁴, antidepressant⁵, anesthetic⁶, antioxidant⁷, insecticidal^{8,9}, anxiolytic¹⁰, anti-inflammatory¹¹ and antimicrobial agents^{12,13}. Literature survey reveals that less attention is given to the synthesis of pyrazoles having a pyran link. They are reported to have useful biological properties such as analgesic and anti-inflammatory¹⁴ and antimicrobial¹⁵.

Synthesis of pyrazoles from 1,3-diketones¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and β -keto ester¹⁹ with hydrazines is well documented. It was decided, therefore, to synthesize new pyrano pyrazoles from 1,3-diketone containing pyrone nucleus which may show much improved or different kinds of biological activities. In a series of papers Cervello *et al.*²⁰ have discussed at length that *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde when treated with triacetic acid lactone undergoes

translactonization to form pyrano pyran-1,3-diketones in one step. Based on these findings we synthesized starting material 8,9-dimethyl-3-acetoacetylpyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione **3** in one step by carrying out the reaction of 6,7-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxycoumarin **1** with triacetic acid lactone **2**. The compound **3** was converted to pyrano pyrazoles **4a-c** upon treatment with hydrazines. It is worth mentioning that starting material **3** is a polyketomethylene compound and complex polyketomethylene compounds have been reported to undergo ring opening reaction with nucleophiles followed by recyclization to afford naturally occurring aromatic and oxygen heterocycles^{21,22}. Besides it, pyrano pyrones have been thoroughly investigated by Scott *et al.*²³ who carried out its transformation under basic conditions, to biogenetically important compounds such as orcinol and other phenolic compounds.

Drugs having anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic properties are one of the most widely used drugs for various medical and surgical conditions to the patients. A large number of drugs having the above effects exist with potent activity but adverse drug reaction also occurs. So, safe drug is required in order to avoid adverse drug reaction. Keeping this in view, the present study

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of compounds 3 and 4c

Organism	Test organisms	Inhibition zone size in mm		
		3 (70 µg/disc)	4c (70 µg/disc)	Antibiotic control ^a (30 µg/disc)
Gram +ve bacteria	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	–	–	22
	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	–	–	21
Gram –ve bacteria	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	10	11	23
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	–	–	–
	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	–	–	16
	<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	10	8.0	23
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	–	–	23

^aAntibiotic control : Chloramphenicol. – No activity detected.

was undertaken to investigate also the antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities of above mentioned compounds, 3 and 4a-c.

Results and discussion

The dione 3 was obtained by heating at 60 °C and stirring an equimolar quantity of 6,7-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxycoumarin 1 and triacetic acid lactone 2 through intramolecular transactonization reaction. The compound was identified on the basis of spectral data (Experimental section) and positive ferric chloride test. The reaction of 3 with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine and hydrazinobenzothiazole conveniently afforded pyrazole derivatives 4a-c (Scheme 1). The compounds were identified on the basis of spectral data. Thus, the IR

spectrum of 4a showed a broad band at 3215 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to NH group. Two sharp bands at 1746 and 1721 cm⁻¹ were assigned to enol lactone and coumarin carbonyl groups, respectively. Two more sharp bands at 1630 and 1559 cm⁻¹ were assigned to >C=N and >C=C< groups, respectively. The ¹H NMR spectrum of 4a exhibited three methyl singlets at δ 2.31, 2.38 and 2.40. The aromatic region of the spectrum clearly showed four singlets each integrating for one proton at δ 6.71, 7.39, 7.79 and 8.42. The up field singlet at δ 6.7 was assigned to Ha proton of pyrazole moiety. The low field singlet at δ 8.42 was assigned to Hb proton (*peri* to carbonyl group) and two singlets at 7.39 and 7.79 were due to two aromatic protons (C-7, C-10). Further confirmation for structure 4a was provided by its mass spectrum, which exhibited

Table 2. Effects of test compounds 3, 4a, 4b, 4c and Diclofenac sodium on cotton pellet induced granuloma

Test Comps.	Dose/kg	Weight of cotton pellets			
		Wet weight	% Inhibition	Dry weight	% Inhibition
DMSO	5 ml	183.7 ± 11.5	–	79.3 ± 3.5	–
3	20 mg	123.0 ± 8.9 ^a	33.04	44.0 ± 3.2 ^a	44.51
4a	20 mg	121.5 ± 8.7 ^a	33.9	33.5 ± 1.9 ^a	55.23
4b	20 mg	84.0 ± 5.2 ^a	54.3	33.5 ± 2.4 ^a	57.8
4c	20 mg	100.0 ± 9.1 ^a	45.6	41.0 ± 2.7 ^a	48.3
Diclofenac sodium	5 mg	84.5 ± 6.3 ^a	54.00	30.0 ± 1.8 ^a	62.2

The results given are mean ± S.E.M; number of animals used (n = 6).

^aP value of < 0.05 was considered as significant in comparison to control.

Note

Scheme 1

M^+ at m/z 322 ($M^+ + 1$ peak at m/z 323). The peak at m/z 307 was due to loss of methyl group from molecular ion peak. The other important peaks were obtained as shown in Scheme 2.

Biological activity :

Antibacterial activity :

The compounds **3** and **4a-c** were screened for antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria using Disc diffusion method²⁴. The compounds **4a**, **4b** did not show any antibacterial activity whereas **3** and **4c** exhibited moderate activity only against Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella dysenteriae* and no activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and other Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* as compared to antibacterial drug Chloramphenicol (Table 1).

Anti-inflammatory activity :

The compounds **3** and **4a-c** were tested for their anti-

inflammatory activity at the dose of 20 mg/kg body weight in male albino rats by the formation of granuloma tissue in cotton pellet induced chronic model of inflammation²⁵. The test compounds and standard drug Diclofenac sodium significantly reduced both wet as well as dry weights in cotton pellet granuloma. The compounds **3** and **4a-c** showed percentage inhibition in dry weight as 44.51, 55.23, 57.8 and 48.3% respectively as compared to Diclofenac sodium 62.2% (Table 2).

Experimental

The melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on Interspec 2020 spectrometer using KBr. The 300 MHz ¹H NMR and high resolution FAB mass spectra were provided by Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility (SAIF), CDRI, Lucknow. The chemical shifts were reported in δ values relative to TMS as internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on glass plates coated with silica gel G (Merck, Germany)

Scheme 2

using benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 1), chloroform-methanol (9 : 1) as mobile phase and visualized by iodine vapour and alcoholic ferric chloride.

6,7-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (1) :

Triethylorthoformate (150 ml) was moist by adding water (20 ml) and shaking in a separating funnel. The aqueous layer was removed and organic layer was transferred to a 250 ml of round bottom flask. To this moist triethylorthoformate, was added a catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid (100 mg) and heated on water bath for 0.5 h. Now 6,7-dimethyl-4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran (5.0 g) was added in portion with simultaneous thorough shaking of the content of the flask. After complete addition was made, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h (completion of the reaction was

checked by TLC). The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and extracted with diethyl ether (40 ml). The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and concentrated. The residue, after evaporation of the ether was crystallized from the chloroform-petrol to give 6,7-dimethyl-4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde 1 as yellow crystalline solid; yield 60%; m.p. 140 °C²⁶.

8,9-Dimethyl-3-acetoacetylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]-benzopyran-2,5-dione (3) :

A mixture of 6,7-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxycoumarin 1 (1.0 g, 4.5 mmol) and triacetic acid lactone 2 (0.57 g, 4.5 mmol) was taken in methanol (30 ml) and stirred at 60 °C for 3 h. A greenish yellow solid 3 deposited. The crystals were filtered, washed with methanol and

Note

dried; yield 66.2%, m.p. 240 °C (Found : C, 66.40; H, 4.35. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$: C, 66.25, H, 4.29%); IR (KBr) : 3377, 1756 and 1720 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.27 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.42 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.88 (1H, s, Ha), 7.26 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.84 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.91 (1H, s, Hb); MS : m/z (%) 327 ($M^+ + 1$, 50), 326 (M^+ , 20), 311 (10), 298 (5), 283 (10), 270 (35), 269 (30), 241 (20), 213 (10), 197 (15), 148 (80), 128 (15), 120 (20).

8,9-Dimethyl-3-(3-methylpyrazol-5-yl)-pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione (4a) :

8,9-Dimethyl-3-acetoacetylpyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione **3** (1.0 g, 3.0 mmol) was dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (1 ml, 20.2 mmol) added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h on an oil bath. On cooling light yellow solid **4a** was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and dried. The filtrate was poured into crushed ice water (50 ml) when more **4a** was collected by filtration. The two solids were combined and purified by recrystallization from chloroform-benzene mixture as yellow shining needles; yield 65%, m.p. 315–320 °C (Found : C, 67.25; H, 4.55; N, 8.85. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{14}N_2O_4$: C, 67.08; H, 4.34; N, 8.69%); IR (KBr) : 3215, 1746, 1721, 1630 and 1559 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 2.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.71 (1H, s, Ha), 8.42 (1H, s, Hb), 7.39 (1H, s, H-7), 7.79 (1H, s, H-10); MS : m/z (%) 323 ($M^+ + 1$, 90), 322 (M^+ , 85), 307 (80), 289 (65), 279 (20), 242 (5), 238 (10), 198 (20), 154 (100).

8,9-Dimethyl-3-(3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-yl)-pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione (4b) :

8,9-Dimethyl-3-acetoacetylpyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione **3** (1.0 g, 3.0 mmol) was taken in acetic acid (20 ml) and phenylhydrazine (1 ml, 10.2 mmol) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on an oil bath for 1 h. On cooling at room temperature yellow solid **4b** was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and dried. The filtrate was poured into crushed ice-water (50 ml) to get more of **4b**. The two solids were combined and purified by recrystallization from chloroform as yellow crystals; yield 70%, m.p. 245–250 °C (Found : C, 72.50; H, 4.74; N, 7.18. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{18}N_2O_4$: C, 72.36; H,

4.52; N, 7.03%); IR (KBr) : 1748, 1721, 1635 and 1559 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 2.34 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.39 (6H, s, 2 CH_3), 6.57 (1H, s, Ha), 7.16–7.81 (8H, m, Ar-H + H-Hb); MS : m/z (%) 398 (M^+ , 100), 397 (20), 370 (10), 357 (5), 241 (5), 213 (5), 209 (5), 189 (5), 185 (5), 181 (5), 165 (10), 161 (5), 148 (35), 132 (10), 120 (10).

8,9-Dimethyl-3-(3-methyl-1-benzothiazolylpyrazol-5-yl)-pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione (4c) :

8,9-Dimethyl-3-acetoacetylpyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione **3** (1.0 g, 3.0 mmol) was dissolved in alcohol (25 ml) containing *p*-toluene sulfonic acid (30 mg) and hydrazinobenzothiazole (0.53 g, 3.0 mmol) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on boiling water bath for 16–18 h. It was cooled at room temperature to afford **4c** as light green crystalline solid. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried; yield 66%, m.p. 285–290 °C (Found : C, 66.12; H, 3.98; N, 9.35. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{17}N_3O_4S$: C, 65.93; H, 3.73; N, 9.23%); IR (KBr) : 1768, 1742, 1684 and 1640 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 2.30 (9H, s, 3 CH_3), 6.48 (1H, s, Ha), 6.97–8.17 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.81 (1H, s, Hb); MS : m/z (%) 455 (M^+ , 100), 427 (10), 411 (5), 399 (10), 321 (2), 308 (5), 153 (70), 167 (10), 123 (3).

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